

Solvatochromism and emission studies of Group 6 tetracarbonyl complexes of *N*-{(2-pyridyl)methyliden}-6-coumarin

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Manuscript received online 26 September 2013, accepted 31 January 2014

Abstract : Tetra-carbonyl Group 6 metal complexes of *N*-{(2-pyridyl)methyliden}-6-coumarin (L), $[M(CO)_4(L)]$, are used to study the effect of solvent polarity on the absorption and emission spectroscopy. The solvents of different polarity of hydroxylic and non-hydroxylic type are used. The MLCT band of the complexes is blue shifted with increasing solvent polarity and show the negative solvatochromism. The critical analysis reveals that the excited state shows lower dipolar property than ground state. This determines the superior solvation of the dipolar ground state and inferior solvation of the less dipolar excited state by polar solvent. Kamlet and Taft's Π^* solvent polarity parameter are used to correlate with high degree of MLCT energies. The fluorescence spectra in different solvents also demonstrate that the emission band is red shifting with increasing solvent polarity.

Keywords : Coumarinyl Schiff base, Group 6 metal carbonyl, negative solvatochromism, absorption spectra, emission spectra.

Introduction

Polypyridine complexes have produced a lot of interest due to their catalyses, photophysics and photochemistry, electrochemistry and supramolecular property¹⁻⁵. Recent years have witnessed a great deal of interest in the synthesis of new ligands in the framework of diimine function. Among them iminopyridine, derived from the condensation of pyridine-2-carboxaldehyde and primary amine (aliphatic and aromatic) are attractive because of their electronic properties⁶⁻⁸. Considerable effort has now been given to synthesise ligands on coumarin backbone so that metal-coumarin complexes may be synthesized that could display interesting excited state properties and be used in designing artificial photosynthetic systems, chemical sensors and molecular level devices⁹⁻¹¹. $[M(CO)_4(\text{diimine})]$ (M = Cr, Mo, W) are of interest because of their photophysical properties, catalytic activities etc.¹²⁻¹⁸. These complexes bear low lying excited states of ligand field (LF) and MLCT origin. The MLCT band is very sensitive to the nature of solvent and substituent^{19,20}.

Group 6 metal carbonyl complexes of *N*-{(2-

pyridyl)methyliden}-6-coumarin (L) have been characterised by us and have potential antioxidant property both in cell free and *in vitro* studies and highest activity is observed to $[W(CO)_4(L)]^{21}$. Herein we wish to report the effect of solvent polarity on absorption and luminescence properties of $[M(CO)_4(L)]$ (L : *N*-{(2-pyridyl)methyliden}-6-coumarin).

Experimental

Materials and physical characterisation :

Coumarin was purchased from S.D. Fine Chem. Ltd., Boisar. $M(CO)_6$ (M = Cr, Mo, W), $Me_3NO \cdot 2H_2O$ and pyridine-2-carboxaldehyde was purchased from Aldrich Chemical Co. *N*-{(2-Pyridyl)methyliden}-6-coumarin were synthesized by equimolar condensation of pyridine-2-carboxaldehyde and 6-amino coumarin in dry methanol. The complexes, $[M(CO)_4(L)]$ were synthesised and characterised following previously reported procedure²¹. Dehydrated Me_3NO was obtained by reduced pressure sublimation of purchased compound. Reactions were carried out under extremely dry oxygen free atmosphere under Atmos bags (Sigma-Aldrich). THF and *n*-heptane

were dried before use²². All other chemicals used were of A.R. quality and were used as received from SRL, India. UV-Vis spectra were recorded from Perkin-Elmer UV-Vis spectrophotometer model Lambda 25 and emission was examined by LS 55 Perkin-Elmer spectrofluorimeter at room temperature (298 K) in acetonitrile solution under degassed condition. Solvatochromism was examined using at best fifteen dry solvents (non-hydroxylic : hexane (Hx), heptane, benzene (Bz), toluene (Tol), dichloromethane (DCM), chloroform (CHCl₃); hydroxylic solvents : tetrahydrofuran (THF), methanol (MeOH), 2-propanol (PropOH), *tert*-butanol (*t*-BuOH), 2-methoxy ethanol (EGME), nitromethane (NME), acetonitrile (AN), *N,N*-dimethylformamide (DMF), dimethylsulfoxide (DMSO) and the plots of E_T (30) versus E_{MLCT} were generated by Origin 6.1. Effect of solvent dipole moment and refractive indices f(D,η²) on the E_{MLCT} were examined²³⁻²⁶.

Results and discussion

Synthesis and formulation :

The reaction of L and M(CO)₆ (M = Cr, Mo, W) (1 : 1 mole proportion) under stirring condition in dry THF and nitrogen environment in presence of two equivalent Me₃NO for a period of 4–6 h has synthesized blue or purple complexes (Scheme 1) following published procedure²¹ (eq. (1)). The ligand, *N*-{(2-pyridyl)methylidene}

6-coumarin (L) is *N, N'* chelating system where N and N' refer to N(pyridyl) and N(imine) donor centres, respectively. The composition of the complexes, [Cr(CO)₄(L)] (1), [Mo(CO)₄(L)] (2) and [W(CO)₄(L)] (3) has been supported by microanalytical, spectroscopic and electrochemical data. The complexes are soluble in polar solvent like DMF as well as non polar solvent like heptane. Solution of [W(CO)₄(L)] in benzene are blue but in DMF are red. They are non-electrolyte and diamagnetic. All the spectroscopic characterisation were characterised using FT-IR, UV-Visible, NMR and fluorescence data as per reported data^{21,27}.

UV-Vis spectra and solvatochromism :

The spectra of the complexes show two characteristic bands, one at shorter wavelength (278–282, 330–334 nm) for intra-ligand charge transfer transition and an intense broad band appears at > 500 nm. This longer wavelength transition is assigned to MLCT band, d(M(0))→π* (ligand) (Fig. 1, Table 1). Data show that the intraligand charge transitions are hardly affected by the change in solvent characteristics. The effect of solvent polarity on this MLCT band has been examined for a series of non-hydroxylic and hydroxylic solvents (Fig. 2). The plots of Reichardt's solvent parameters, E_T (30)^{23,24} versus the E_{MLCT} are

Scheme 1. Binding mode of the ligand (L) and structure of the complexes.

Fig. 1. UV-Vis spectra of [a] [Cr(CO)₄(L)] (1) (—), [b] [Mo(CO)₄(L)] (2) (---) and [c] [W(CO)₄(L)] (3) (.....) in CH₃CN (inset figure at higher concentration).

Table 1. UV-Vis spectral data of the complexes in different solvent

Solvent	UV-Vis spectral data, λ_{\max} (nm)		
	[Cr(CO) ₄ (L)] (1)	[Mo(CO) ₄ (L)] (2)	[W(CO) ₄ (L)] (3)
<i>n</i> -Heptane	599, 360, 289	563, 353	611, 406, 336, 292
<i>n</i> -Hexane	577, 360, 277, 235	595, 346, 269	610, 339, 278, 228
Toluene	609, 364, 294, 285	575, 350, 285	584, 344, 286
Benzene	608, 365, 283	571, 354, 280	580, 344, 282
Chloroform	607, 364, 281, 245	573, 349, 284	581, 341, 280, 247
Dichloromethane	589, 365, 282, 241	553, 352, 281, 247	565, 336, 280, 244
Tetrahydrofuran	581, 374, 274	542, 349, 285, 253	555, 336, 283, 246
2-Propanol	554, 368	519, 357	537, 369
Methanol	567, 367, 280, 241	516, 367, 284	545, 360, 279, 244
2-Methoxyethanol	557, 376, 285, 255	532, 362, 285, 253	547, 336, 282, 248
Nitromethane	550, 386	512, 393	527, 390
Acetonitrile	548, 368, 280, 242	511, 338, 281, 246	525, 336, 278, 245
Dimethylformamide	544, 379, 280	506, 351, 287, 268	524, 328, 275
Dimethylsulphoxide	539, 380, 286, 261	497, 373, 285, 268	517, 335, 283, 259

[W(CO)₄(L)] (3) showing different colour in different solvent : [1] benzene, [2] toluene, [3] chloroform, [4] tetrahydrofuran, [5] dichloromethane, [6] *t*-butanol, [7] methanol, [8] dimethylformamide, [9] acetonitrile, [10] dimethylsulfoxide

Fig. 2. Absorption spectra of [W(CO)₄(L)] (3) in visible region (> 400 nm) in different solvent (showing negative solvatochromism) : [a] acetonitrile, [b] dichloromethane, [c] chloroform, [d] benzene, [e] tetrahydrofuran, [f] toluene, [g] methanol, [h] dimethylformamide, [i] 2-methoxyethanol, [j] dimethylsulfoxide, [k] 2-propanol, [l] nitromethane, [m] *n*-heptane and [n] *n*-hexane.

linear (Fig. 3). The effect of solvent polarity is examined by plotting E_{MLCT} versus $f(D, \eta^2)$ of different solvents (D = dipole moment; η = refractive index)²⁸⁻³⁰. Positive slopes of the plots (Figs. 3 and 4) support the low dipolar property of the complexes at excited state than that of ground state (Table 2). With increasing solvent polarity the MLCT band is blue shifted (Tables 1 and 2)

Fig. 3. Energies of the MLCT absorption (E_{MLCT}) of $[W(CO)_4(L)]$ plotted against $E_T(30)$ values : (1) hexane, (2) heptane, (3) toluene, (4) benzene, (5) tetrahydrofuran, (6) chloroform, (7) dichloromethane, (8) dimethylsulphoxide, (9) acetonitrile, (10) nitromethane, (11) 2-propanol, (12) 2-methoxyethanol and (13) methanol.

and in general the solvent effect is described by negative solvatochromism. The MLCT band shows shifting > 70 nm on changing the solvent polarity (Fig. 2) (λ_{max} (toluene), 609 nm and (λ_{max} (DMSO), 539 nm for $[Cr(CO)_4(L)]$). This can be attributed to superior solvation of the dipolar ground state and inferior solvation of the less dipolar excited state by polar solvent. The electronic transition

Fig. 4. Energies of the MLCT absorption (E_{MLCT}) of $[W(CO)_4(L)]$ plotted against $f(D, \eta^2)$ values : (1) benzene, (2) toluene, (3) hexane, (4) chloroform, (5) tetrahydrofuran, (6) dichloromethane, (7) 2-methoxyethanol, (8) 2-propanol, (9) dimethylformamide, (10) nitromethane, (11) acetonitrile and (12) methanol.

Table 2. Solvent dependence of metal to ligand charge-transfer absorption maxima of $[M(CO)_4(L)]$ (1-3) complexes at 298 K

Solvent	E_{MLCT} (kcal mol ⁻¹)			$E_T(30)$ (kcal mol ⁻¹)	Π^*	$f(D, n^2)$
	$[Cr(CO)_4(L)]$ (1)	$[Mo(CO)_4(L)]$ (2)	$[W(O)_4(L)]$ (3)			
<i>n</i> -Heptane	51.1	54.92	46.83	31.1		
<i>n</i> -Hexane	51.0	54.8	47.06	31.0		0.035
Toluene	46.99	50.2	48.99	33.9	0.54	0.026
Benzene	47.14	50.03	49.34	34.3	0.59	0.005
Chloroform	47.3	50.03	49.25	39.1	0.58	0.305
Dichloromethane	48.58	51.75	50.83	40.7	0.83	0.434
Tetrahydrofuran	49.34	52.6	51.56	37.4	0.58	0.418
2-Propanol	51.93	55.24	52.99	48.4	0.46	0.546
Methanol	50.29	55.03	52.6	55.4	0.60	0.616
2-Methoxyethanol	51.75	57.23	52.31	52		0.516
Nitromethane	52.03	56.11	54.5	46.3	0.85	0.582
Acetonitrile	52.31	56.11	54.61	45.6	0.75	0.610
Dimethylformamide	52.7	56.78	54.71	43.2	0.88	0.548
Dimethylsulphoxide	53.19	57.69	55.46	45.1	1.00	

may change the dipolar property of the molecule; decrease in dipole moment may influence the excited state in a solvent cage of oriented dipoles for imperfect disposal to stabilize the excited state. The change in geometry by the solvation process is excluded via hydrogen bonding as the band structure of the CT transition remains unchanged in the non-hydrogen bonded solvent. Kamlet and Taft's Π^* solvent polarity parameter¹⁹ are also used to correlate with high degree MLCT transition energies. The resultant correlations are shown in Fig. 5. On the other hand the high energy transitions are almost

Fig. 5. Energies of MLCT absorption (E_{MLCT}) of $[W(CO)_4(L)]$ plotted against π^* value : (1) 2-propanol, (2) toluene, (3) chloroform, (4) benzene, (5) THF, (6) methanol, (7) acetonitrile, (8) dichloromethane, (9) nitromethane, (10) dimethylformamide and (11) dimethylsulphoxide.

independent of solvent polarity (Fig. 6). DFT calculation of these three complexes has been performed using optimized structures by Gaussian 03 analyses package. The structural agreement has been observed from the comparison of bond distances and angles between calculated and X-ray determined structures²¹. Molecular functions are composed of metal, CO and L; the HOMO to HOMO-2 are dominated by metal and CO functions (Cr, 59–66% and CO, 30–33% in $[Cr(CO)_4(L)]$ (1); Mo, 50–65% and CO, 32–37% in $[Mo(CO)_4(L)]$ (2); W, 50–62% and CO, 32–39% in $[W(CO)_4(L)]$ (3)) while LUMO to LUMO+2 are exclusively contributed from L (>85%). The HOMO

Fig. 6. Absorption spectra of $[W(CO)_4(L)]$ (3) in UV region (< 400 nm) in different solvent (showing no significant change at high energy transition) : [a] acetonitrile, [b] dichloromethane, [c] chloroform, [d] tetrahydrofuran, [e] methanol, [f] 2-methoxyethanol, [g] *n*-hexane and [h] *t*-butanol.

→ LUMO is considered as major transition which is $M(d\pi)/CO(\pi) \rightarrow L(\pi^*)$ transition. So the transition energy should be influenced by the polarity of environment. The contribution of function of CO enhances the polarity of the HOMO and the energy difference between HOMO and LUMO decreases ongoing down the Group 6 (Fig. 7). The intensity of these transitions has been assessed

Fig. 7. HOMO-LUMO energy gap with probable charge transfer transition of $[M(CO)_4(L)]$.

Table 3. Solvent dependent emission maxima of the complexes

Solvent	[Cr(CO) ₄ (L)] (1)		[Mo(CO) ₄ (L)] (2)		[W(CO) ₄ (L)] (3)	
	λ_{ex} (nm)	λ_{em} (nm)	λ_{ex} (nm)	λ_{em} (nm)	λ_{ex} (nm)	λ_{em} (nm)
<i>n</i> -Heptane	360	453	353	421	336	450
<i>n</i> -Hexane	360	454	346	455	339	453
Toluene	364	471	350	480	344	470
Benzene	365	472	354	486	344	474
Chloroform	364	478	349	492	341	482
Dichloromethane	365	485	352	500	336	482
Tetrahydrofuran	374	507	349	502	336	503
2-Propanol	368	530	357	524	369	526
Methanol	367	549	367	543	360	540
2-Methoxyethanol	376	531	362	523	336	519
Nitromethane	386	496	393	482	390	477
Acetonitrile	368	517	338	523	336	511
Dimethylformamide	379	537	351	529	328	530
Dimethylsulphoxide	380	546	373	538	335	538

λ_{ex} = Excitation wavelength; λ_{em} = Emission wavelength.

from oscillator strength (*f*). The experimental observation supports indeed.

Emission spectra :

The complexes, [M(CO)₄(L)] exhibit high intense emission than that of free L. The excitation is assigned to π - π^* transition at 330–334 nm (Table 3, Fig. 8). However, the complexes do not show any emission when they

Fig. 8. Fluorescence spectra of [a] [Cr(CO)₄(L)] (1) (—), [b] [Mo(CO)₄(L)] (2) (---) and [c] [W(CO)₄(L)] (3) (.....) in CH₃CN.

are excited at MLCT wavelength (> 500 nm). High emission intensity in chelation phase may be offered by the rigidity of the chelate ring. Intersystem crossing due to spin-orbit coupling introduced by the metal centre may also influence the emission intensity. This happens to the Group-6 metal carbonyl complexes of L. The quantum yields (ϕ) vary 0.02 to 0.03. [M(CO)₄(L)] complexes show higher quantum yield than L ($\phi = 0.018$)²⁷. The excitation to the π - π^* state followed by rapid internal conversion to the penetrated MLCT state (assumes to be the lowest energy excited state) may be responsible for emission. However, it appears that the emission in these complexes is occurring from the high energy π - π^* state which has been ruled out the possibility of competitive energy transfer to the MLCT state. The emission spectra show the solvent polarity dependency. In low polar solvent like hexane, heptane the emission maxima are almost same for the complexes whereas in polar solvent like dimethylformamide and dimethylsulfoxide the emission maxima shift to longer wavelength than hexane ($\Delta\lambda \sim 100$ nm) (Table 3, Fig. 9).

Fig. 9. Fluorescence spectra of $[W(CO)_4(L)]$ (3) in different solvent : (1) acetonitrile, (2) dichloromethane, (3) chloroform, (4) benzene, (5) tetrahydrofuran, (6) toluene, (7) methanol, (8) dimethylformamide, (9) 2-methoxyethanol, (10) dimethylsulfoxide, (11) 2-propanol, (12) nitromethane, (13) *n*-heptane, (14) *n*-hexane and (15) *t*-butanol.

Conclusion

The absorption spectra of $[M(CO)_4(L)]$ ($M = Cr^0, Mo^0, W^0$; $L = N\text{-}\{(2\text{-pyridyl)methylidene}\}\text{-6-coumarin}$) exhibit negative solvatochromism. The emission band is also shifted to longer wavelength with increasing solvent polarity. This accounts the superior solvation of the dipolar ground state and inferior solvation of the less dipolar excited state by polar solvent. The electronic transition may change the dipolar property of the molecule; decrease in dipole moment may influence the excited state in a solvent cage of oriented dipoles for imperfect disposal to stabilize the excited state.

Acknowledgements

Financial support from Council of Scientific and Industrial Research (CSIR), New Delhi is gratefully acknowledged.

References

1. K. Kalyansundaram, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1982, **46**, 159.
2. R.-Q. Fan, D.-S. Zhu, Y. Mu, G.-H. Li, Y.-L. Yang, Q. Su and S.-H. Feng, *Eur. J. Inorg. Chem.*, 2004, 4891.
3. V. W.-W. Yam, Y.-L. Pui and K.-K. Cheung, *J. Chem.*

- Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 2000, 3658.
4. Y. Wang, X.-M. Ouyang, Y.-Z. Li and W.-Y. Sun, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 2003, **76**, 1403.
5. H.-F. Zhu, L. Li, T. Okamura, W. Zhao, W.-Y. Sun and N. Ueyama, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 2003, **76**, 761.
6. L. A. Garcia-Escudero, D. Miguel and J. A. Turiel, *J. Organomet. Chem.*, 2006, **691**, 3434.
7. M. Menon, A. Pramanik and A. Chakravorty, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1995, **34**, 3310.
8. A. Mendes, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1999, **24**, 77.
9. V. Balzani, A. Juris, M. Venturi, S. Campagna and S. Serroni, *Chem. Rev.*, 1996, **96**, 759.
10. A. El-Ghayoury, A. Harriman, A. Khatyr and R. Ziessel, *J. Phys. Chem. (A)*, 2000, **104**, 1512.
11. A. Juris and L. Prodi, *New J. Chem.*, 2001, **25**, 1132.
12. A. Mendes, M. Sarbay, B. Hazer and H. Arslan, *Appl. Organomet. Chem.*, 2005, **19**, 76.
13. A. Vlcek (Jr.), *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 2002, **230**, 225 and references therein.
14. Q. Ye, Q. Wu, H. Zhao, Y.-M. Song, X. Xue, R.-G. Xiong, S.-M. Peng and G.-H. Lee, *J. Organomet. Chem.*, 2005, **690**, 286.
15. V. N. Nemykin, J. G. Olsen, E. Perera and P. Basu, *Inorg. Chem.*, 2006, **45**, 3557.
16. E. Bayram and S. Ozkar, *J. Organomet. Chem.*, 2006, **691**, 3267.
17. F. Alper, C. Kayram and S. Ozkar, *J. Organomet. Chem.*, 2006, **691**, 2734.
18. R. W. Balk, T. Snoeck, D. J. Stufkens and A. Oskam, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1980, **19**, 3015.
19. D. M. Manuta and A. J. Lees, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1986, **25**, 3212.
20. Y. Che, X. Tian, H. Chen, Z. Tang and J. Lin, *New J. Chem.*, 2006, **30**, 883.
21. P. Datta, A. P. Mukhopadhyay, P. Manna, E. R. T. Tiekink, P. C. Sil and C. Sinha, *J. Inorg. Biochem.*, 2011, **105**, 577.
22. A. I. Vogel, "A Text Book of Practical Organic Chemistry", Longmann, London, 1959.
23. C. Reichardt, *Chem. Rev.*, 1994, **94**, 2319.
24. C. Reichardt, "Solvents and Solvent Effects in Organic Chemistry", 2nd ed., VCH, Weinheim, 1988.
25. G. A. Crosby and J. N. Demas, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1971, **75**, 991.
26. D. V. O'Connor and D. Phillips, "Time Correlated Single Photon Counting", Academic Press, New York,

- 1984.
27. S. Roy, T. K. Mondal, P. Mitra, E. L. Torres and C. Sinha, *Polyhedron*, 2011, **30**, 913.
28. Y. Marcus, "Ion Solvation", John Wiley, Chichester, 1985.
29. Y. Y. Akhadov, "Dielectric Properties of Binary Solutions – A Data Hand Book", Pergamon Press, Oxford, 1981.
30. B. Valeur, "Modern Luminescence Spectroscopy", ed. G. Schulman, John Wiley & Sons Inc., 1993.